

Effects of Soil Moisture Conservation and Nutrient Management on Soil Water Content and WUE of Grain Sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* L. Moench) in Eastern Ethiopia

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ABSTRACT:

Water and nutrients are the most constraining factors in sorghum production in semiarids of eastern Ethiopia. Combining soil moisture conservation and nutrient management practices may reduce these limitations. The study was carried out to explore the effects of combining soil moisture preservation and integrated nutrient management practices on soil water content and water-use efficiency (WUE) of grain sorghum. A split plot experiment was conducted at Babile and Erer districts amid the 2017 cropping season. Main plots were assigned to soil moisture conservation practices (flatbed and tied ridge) and the sub-plots were assigned to six nutrient combinations of 0N0P kg + t FYM; 46N10P kg + t FYM ha⁻¹; 0N0P kg + 5 t FYM ha⁻¹; 23N5P kg + 2.5 t FYM ha⁻¹; 46N10P kg + 2.5 t FYM ha⁻¹ and 23N5P kg + 5 t FYM ha⁻¹. Treatments were randomized in a Randomized Complete Block Design with three replications. The sorghum variety 'Teshale' was used as a test crop. The results uncovered that both biomass and grain water-use efficiencies considerably improved with tied ridges coordinates with NP and FYM than other treatments. Tied ridges combined with 46N10P kg + 2.5 t FYM ha⁻¹ and 23N5P kg + 5 t FYM ha⁻¹ were way better than those of tied edges. The tied edges with 46N10P kg + 2.5 t FYM ha⁻¹ (M5) as compared to unfertilized flatbeds, had brought about approximately 110 and 99% increment in biomass WUE and around 114 and 124% increment in grain WUE at Babile and Erer areas, respectively. Essentially, soil water content was higher for tied ridges amended with FYM and integrated NP and FYM as compared to other treatments. We, hence, concluded that combining moisture conservation impacts with the integrated nutrient amendment would improve soil water content and water-use efficiency of grain sorghum in eastern Ethiopia.

Keywords: farmyard manure, flatbed, in-situ rainwater harvesting, NP fertilizers, semi-arid, tied-ridge.

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INTRODUCTION

Agricultural production in Sub-Saharan Africa primarily relies on rainfed production that is climate-sensitive. The most limiting factor to crop production in the arid and semiarid areas of Ethiopia especially eastern Hararghe is the availability of soil moisture and soil fertility. The low rainfall together with its unreliability and poor distribution severely affects crop production [1]. Additionally, the low quality of soil resource base which has been due to inherent and induced deficiencies of major nutrients such as nitrogen and phosphorous and low organic matter negatively affect crop production. Moreover, there is a high risk of very low production levels or even crop failure, particularly under poor management of water and soil resources [1,2].

Sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench), a high-value traditional crop of the drylands, is considered the crop for the future that can contribute to food security. This crop has the potential to diversify the farming systems, adapt to spread risks and is more resilient to weather variations and climate change. Improving sorghum productivity is thus crucial to resolving food crises, enhancing food security and improving income for the most vulnerable people of drylands. Grain sorghum tolerates and avoids drought more than many other cereal crops, but the drought response of sorghum does not come without a yield loss and the yield reduction due to water stress at the vegetative and reproductive stages could reach about 36% and 55%, respectively. Thus, focusing on techniques that can improve water availability in the sorghum growing season alone can double the current dryland sorghum yield with the existing genetic potential [3,4].

In Ethiopia, the area under grain sorghum is mainly concentrated in semiarids of Oromia, Amhara, Tigray, SNNP and Benishanglu regions [1]. Limited and erratic rainfall in these rainfed regions makes sorghum vulnerable to moisture stress during its growth and development stages, resulting in high yield reductions [5]. Grain production shortfalls in eastern Ethiopia are commonly associated with the occurrence of intra-seasonal dry spells or droughts that adversely affect crop yields. The main limitation in increasing grain yields in rainfed farming systems of drought-prone areas is crop water stress caused by inefficient use of total available seasonal rainwater. Inefficient use of rainwater is often a consequence of poor rainfall partitioning resulting in low soil moisture in the plant root zone and/ or poor plant uptake of available soil moisture [6]. To ensure increased crop production and food security, conservation and judicious use of soil and water play an important role, especially in semi-arid regions. In Ethiopia, there is little scope for increasing the area available for crop cultivation to meet the food requirements of the increasing population. The only alternative is to increase crop productivity per unit area per unit time which could result in increased food production. This can be achieved through scientific management of soil and water resources.

In-situ rainwater harvesting techniques increase the amount of moisture stored in the soil profile by trapping or holding rainwater where it falls [7], thereby delaying the onset and occurrence of severe water stress buffering the crop against damage caused by water deficits during dry periods [8]. This effect can best be achieved using ridge ridges. On the other hand, the application of manures and composts improves the physical, chemical and biological properties of the soil in addition to improving the efficient use of applied fertilizers [9]. Therefore, we hypothesized that to derive maximum benefit from water-conserving tillage systems, it is also necessary to optimize soil nutrient status. With this objective in mind, a study was planned to investigate the effects of combined soil moisture conservation technique with integrated application of NP and FYM on growth, yield and WUE of grain sorghum in semiarids of eastern Ethiopia.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Description of Study Sites

A field experiment was conducted at two locations (i.e., the Babile research sub-station of Haramaya University and the Erer research sub-station of Fedis Agricultural Research Center of Oromia Region) during the 2017 main cropping season. The soil class of the study area belongs to the Regosol and RegoArenosol association, Lithosol, Nitosol, and Fluvisol and their associations are the major soil types found in the study area. The soil texture is dominantly sandy loam and the sites are situated within dry semi-arid agroecology often stricken by drought of long dry spells and short wet

seasons (June to August). The rainfall at the Babile site during the experiment period (June to October 2017) totalled 438 mm, while 398 mm was at Erer with the monthly rainfalls being higher in July and August (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Total Monthly Rainfall (mm) During 2017 Cropping Season of Sorghum

Treatments and experimental design

Two land preparation techniques (i.e., flatbed and tied-ridge tillage) as in-situ rainwater conservation were assigned to the main plots and the six nutrient amendments were assigned to sub-plots. The six nutrient treatments included a control or 0N0P kg + 0 t FYM ha⁻¹; 46N10P kg + 0 t FYM ha⁻¹; 0N0P kg + 5 t FYM ha⁻¹; 23N5P kg + 2.5 t FYM ha⁻¹; 46N10P kg + 2.5 t FYM ha⁻¹ and 23N5P kg + 5 t FYM ha⁻¹. The experiment adopted a split-plot design in randomized complete blocks and replicated three times. The test crop was an improved sorghum variety locally called 'Teshale'.

Experimental procedures and management

The land was ploughed by a tractor and levelled manually by hoe. Besides, for the tied ridges, cross-ties of 20 cm height at 1.8 m intervals closed at both ends were raised manually with hand hoe two weeks before planting. Buffer spacing of 1.5 m between blocks to eliminate the effects of lateral movement of water between the tied ridge and flatbed treatments was left with a 1 m wide path, which separated the sub-plots. Each sub-plot was 3.75 m wide and 3.6 m long having a plot area of 13.5 m². Recommended spacing of 75 cm between rows and 15 cm between plants was maintained to accommodate the used plant population of 88,888 plants ha⁻¹. During land preparation, the farmyard manure was spread and incorporated manually as per manure treatments in respective sub-plots two weeks before planting. Half of N was applied at planting and the remaining half was top dressed at 35 DAS (days after sowing), while the whole of P rates were applied at planting.

Planting of sorghum variety *Teshale*, an early maturity type, was carried out on 29 May 2017 at Babile and on 28 June 2017 at Erer. Seeds were hand drilled in the rows at a specified spacing in the flatbeds and furrows for tied-ridge treatment. Seedlings were thinned to one plant per hole at 25 DAS to ensure the targeted plant population as mentioned above. The outermost rows at both sides of the plots and one plant from each end side of rows were considered as borders. The central three rows of each plot were designated as sampling rows or net plots. Weeds were controlled manually first at two weeks after emergence and repeated as needed. Maintenance of the tied ridges was also attempted.

Data Collection

Grain and biomass yield

The whole plants from the central three rows of net plots were harvested at the ground surface and sun-dried for 3 weeks, weighed by balance, and converted to kg ha⁻¹ to determine total above-ground dry-biomass [or biological yield]. Then all the heads of these plants were cut, threshed and weighed, and were adjusted to 12.5% moisture content to obtain grain yield (kg ha⁻¹).

Determination of soil water content and efficiency of moisture conservation

To determine soil water content and efficiency of soil moisture conservation, soil samples were taken from 0-20th cm, 20-40th cm and 40-60th cm depth within the soil profile segment (Fig. 2) from each plot in central rows using a core sampler. Samples were immediately sealed into plastic bags and transported to the laboratory for gravimetric soil water content determination by drying in an oven at 80 °C for 24 hrs. The values were converted to volumetric soil water content by multiplying the gravimetric soil water content by the bulk density of soil cores determined for each segment of soil profile depth [10]. Soil samples for moisture content determination were taken three times (i.e., at planting, heading and maturity stages of the crop). Soil moisture content (%) was determined as prescribed in Eq. 1.

$$MC = [(Ww - Wd) / Wd] * 100 \quad (1)$$

Where, MC = soil moisture content (%), Ww = weight of wet soil (g), and Wd = weight of oven-dry soil (g).

The efficiency of soil moisture conservation was determined for each period as indicated in Eq. 2.

$$E = [M_2 / (M_1 + P)] * 100 \quad (2)$$

Where, *E* = Efficiency of moisture conservation, *M*₁ = moisture content at the beginning of the cropping period, *M*₂ = Moisture content at the end of the cropping period, and *P* = Precipitation received during the cropping period.

Figure 2. The Three Soil Sampling Depths for Soil Moisture Content Determination

Water use efficiency

To determine the water use efficiency of grain sorghum, first crop water use (evapotranspiration, ET) was calculated from rainfall received during the cropping period (P) and change in soil water storage (ΔS). The change in soil water storage (ΔS) was calculated by subtracting soil water content at the end of the cropping period (M_2) from soil water content at the beginning of the cropping period (M_1). Thus, ΔS stood as:

$$\Delta S = M_1 - M_2 \quad (3)$$

Assuming no or negligible losses as runoff and drainage below the root zone, ET was calculated using the following formula (Lopez, 1996):

$$ET = P + \Delta S \quad (4)$$

The water use efficiency of sorghum was determined for both grain and above-ground dry-biomass yield per unit of water used (ET) as per Eq. 5 and 6, respectively.

$$WUE_{GRAIN} [kg ha^{-1} mm^{-1}] = Grain\ yield / ET \quad (5)$$

$$WUE_{BIOMASS} [kg ha^{-1} mm^{-1}] = Dry\ biomass\ yield / ET \quad (6)$$

Where, WUE_{GRAIN} = water use efficiency in grain yield of sorghum per unit of water used, and $WUE_{BIOMASS}$ = water use efficiency in above-ground dry-biomass yield of sorghum per unit of water used.

Data Analysis

Data for each character were subjected to analysis of variance using the GLM procedure of SAS software version 9.1 [11]. Effects were considered significant in all statistical calculations if the table P-values were < 0.05 . The data were combined over locations after carrying out an analysis of variance (ANOVA) for each location separately, and homogeneity was tested (the ratio of larger mean squares to smaller mean squares) as suggested by Gomez and Gomez [12]. If variances across locations were homogeneous, a combined analysis was done, otherwise separately analyzed. Means were separated using Fisher's least significant difference (LSD) and Pearson correlation was calculated to examine relationships between soil water content, yield and water use efficiency.

RESULTS

Various parameters such as a change in soil-water content (ΔS), efficiency of moisture conservation (E), volumetric soil-water content (W%v) and water use efficiency (WUE) of soil-water characteristics and crop water-use were studied and the results are presented and discussed in this section.

Soil Water Content and Efficiency of Soil Moisture Conservation

The independent analysis of data from Babile showed the main effects of soil moisture conservation and nutrient management on ΔS , E and W (%v) to be significant. Besides, the interaction effects of treatments were significant only for volumetric soil-water content during the planting period (Table 1). Similarly, data for the Erer location showed that the main effects of nutrient management on ΔS , E and W (%v) and those of soil moisture conservation on W (%v) at the beginning of the growing season were significant ($P < 0.05$) (Table 1). Moreover, the interaction effects between soil moisture

conservation and nutrient management on ΔS and E were significant except for volumetric soil-water content (Table 1).

Table 1. Mean Squares of ANOVA of Some Soil Water Parameters Data as a Function of Soil Moisture Conservation and Nutrient Management at Babile and Erer During the 2017 Cropping Season

Source	DF	Mean squares							
		Babile				Erer			
		ET	ΔS	E	W (%v)	ET	ΔS	E	W (%v)
REP	2	4.22	4.22	0.19	7.50	1.903	1.903	0.111	1.42
SMC	1	249.11**	249.11**	11.27**	468.29**	25.1 ^{NS}	25.1 ^{NS}	1.42 ^{NS}	60.81*
Error REP*SMC	2	0.57	0.57	0.024	1.02	1.422	1.422	0.08	2.656
NM	5	3.25***	3.25***	0.146***	7.72***	1.04***	1.04***	0.06***	1.9***
SMC*NM	5	0.51 ^{NS}	0.51 ^{NS}	0.022 ^{NS}	0.97*	0.301*	0.301*	0.018*	0.104 ^{NS}
Error REP*SMC*NM	20	0.31	0.31	0.014	0.27	0.093	0.093	0.0054	0.082
CV%		0.12	4.82	4.68	3.26	0.08	4.01	3.96	2.61

Note: *, **, *** are significant at $P < 0.05$, $P < 0.01$ and $P < 0.001$, respectively, NS = non-significant at $P > 0.05$, SMC = soil moisture conservation, NM = nutrient management, ET = evapotranspiration or crop water use, ΔS = the change in soil moisture content (i.e., the difference between moisture content at planting and moisture content at maturity), E = efficiency of moisture conservation practice and W (%v) = soil-water content in the top 60 cm soil depth at planting period.

At Babile, tied ridge planting recorded significantly higher ΔS (59%) and E (56.5%) than flatbed planting (Table 2). Similarly, the integrated application of NP and FYM regardless of their rates had recorded higher ΔS and E over the sole application of NP in full rate. The highest mean ΔS and E values were recorded for the integrated application of 23N5P kg + 5 t FYM ha⁻¹, although these applications were at par with those of the 5 t FYM ha⁻¹ application. Moreover, the ΔS and E calculated for 46N10P kg + 2.5 t FYM ha⁻¹ were at par with those of 23N5P kg + 2.5 t FYM ha⁻¹. Likewise, ΔS and E recorded for sole NP application were at par with those of unfertilized control (Table 2). Overall, the increase achieved in ΔS and E values with 23N5P kg + 5 t FYM ha⁻¹ compared to control were 15.2% and 15.5%, respectively. At Erer location, the water stored at the beginning of the growing season was higher under tied ridge treatment as compared to those of flatbed planting. Moreover, tied ridge treatments supplied with integrated NP and FYM resulted in higher soil-water content followed by those of tied ridge treatments amended with sole FYM as compared to other treatments (Table 3).

Table 2. Effect of Soil Moisture Conservation and Nutrient Management on Moisture Retention and Moisture Conservation Efficiency at Babile During 2017 Cropping Season

Treatments	ΔS	E
<i>Soil moisture conservation</i>		
Flatbed	8.91b	1.98b
Tied ridge	14.17a	3.1a
LSD (0.05)	1.08	0.22
<i>Nutrient management</i>		
0N0P0FYM ha ⁻¹	10.82c	2.39c
46N10P kg ha ⁻¹	10.53c	2.32c
5 t FYM ha ⁻¹	12.03ab	2.64ab
23N5P kg + 2.5 t FYM ha ⁻¹	11.65b	2.56b
46N10P kg + 2.5 t FYM ha ⁻¹	11.77b	2.59b
23N5P kg + 5 t FYM ha ⁻¹	12.46a	2.73a
LSD (0.05)	0.67	0.143
CV (%)	4.82	4.68

Note: Means followed by the same letter in a column are not significantly different at $P > 0.05$, ΔS = change in moisture storage between the beginning and end of the growing season, E = Efficiency of soil moisture conservation, LSD = least significant difference and CV = coefficient of variation.

Undoubtedly, the efficiency of soil moisture conservation was higher in tied ridges than in flatbeds with FYM scaling up it further, regardless of rates and NP combination. Moreover, the efficiency of moisture conservation and soil-water content recorded at planting with sole NP application regardless of water conservation practice were at par with unfertilized control. The unfertilized tied ridge was as good as the flatbed supplied with NP and FYM. Flatbeds amended with sole NP and unfertilized flatbed treatments recorded minimum efficiency of moisture conservation and volumetric soil-water content (Table 3). As compared to unfertilized flatbed treatment, tied ridge with 23N5P kg + 5 t FYM ha⁻¹ application increased the efficiency of soil-water conservation by 37.8%.

Table 3. Effects of Interaction of Treatments on Moisture Conservation Efficiency and Soil-Water Content at Erer Location During the 2017 Growing Season

Soil-moisture conservation	Nutrient Management	E	W (%v)
Flatbed	0N0P0FYM ha ⁻¹	1.62 ^d	9.06 ^e
	46N10P kg ha ⁻¹	1.61 ^d	9.18 ^e
	5 t FYM ha ⁻¹	1.72 ^{cd}	10.08 ^d
	23N5P kg + 2.5 t FYM ha ⁻¹	1.65 ^{cd}	9.85 ^d
	46N10P kg + 2.5 t FYM ha ⁻¹	1.61 ^d	9.65 ^d
	23N5P kg + 5 t FYM ha ⁻¹	1.77 ^c	10.21 ^c
Tied-ridge	0N0P0FYM ha ⁻¹	1.88 ^c	11.53 ^c
	46N10P kg ha ⁻¹	1.89 ^c	11.43 ^c
	5 t FYM ha ⁻¹	2.14 ^{ab}	12.73 ^b
	23N5P kg + 2.5 t FYM ha ⁻¹	2.05 ^b	12.28 ^b
	46N10P kg + 2.5 t FYM ha ⁻¹	2.16 ^{ab}	12.57 ^b
	23N5P kg + 5 t FYM ha ⁻¹	2.23 ^a	13.09 ^a
LSD (0.05)		0.126	0.488
CV (%)		3.96	2.61

Note: Means followed by the same letter within a column are not significantly different at P > 0.05, LSD = least significant difference, CV = coefficient of variation, E = efficiency of soil moisture conservation, W (%v) = volumetric soil-water content at the beginning of plant growth.

The combined analysis results showed that the integrated use of soil moisture conservation and nutrient management significantly improved the soil-water contents recorded at the heading and maturity stages of the crop. The tied ridge supplied with a full dose of FYM, regardless of NP, retained more water in the upper 60 cm soil depth. However, tied ridges amended with 23N5P kg + 5 t FYM ha⁻¹ recorded the maximum volumetric soil-water content followed by that in tied ridges amended with 5 t FYM ha⁻¹. For both recording periods, unfertilized flatbed treatment had the lowest soil-water content. Overall, the volumes of soil-water retained in the upper 60 cm soil depth due to tied ridges supplied with 23N5P kg + 5 t FYM ha⁻¹ were 61 and 84% higher over unfertilized flatbed during the heading and maturity stages of the crop, respectively. Further, the volumetric soil-water contents at all depths were higher in tied ridge treatment than that of flatbed, which decreased with the advancing growth stages (Table 4). Almost similar were the trends of change at different soil depths with advancing phenological growth with higher levels of combined fertility levels being more effective. Thus, the maximum values of soil-water content at each soil depth were obtained under the combined application of 23N5P kg + 5 t FYM ha⁻¹. In general, integrating NP and FYM, regardless of their dose, resulted in higher soil water retention compared to unfertilized control (Table 4).

Table 4. Effect of Soil Moisture Conservation and Nutrient Management on Volumetric Soil-Water Content in Different Soil Depths and Growth Stages of Sorghum During 2017 at Babile.

Treatment	W ₁ %v		W ₂ %v			W ₃ %v
	d ₂	d ₃	d ₁	d ₂	d ₃	d ₁
SMC						
Flatbed	11.45b	7.97b	7.45b	8.53b	7.59a	2.66b
Tied-ridge	18.02a	14.91a	10.54a	11.17a	12.01a	4.85a
LSD (0.05)	0.83	1.05	0.72	2.436	6.48	1.37
NM						

M1	13.77d	10.5d	8.26c	8.83c	8.86c	3.25c
M2	13.84cd	10.55cd	8.33c	9.23c	9.22c	3.59b
M3	14.87bc	11.88ab	9.54a	10.2b	10.44a	3.94a
M4	14.58bcd	12.01ab	9.01b	9.99b	9.9b	3.83ab
M5	15.25ab	11.36bc	9.12b	10.14b	9.83b	3.9a
M6	16.11a	12.35a	9.71a	10.71a	10.56a	4.02a
LSD (0.05)	1.07	0.82	0.33	0.46	0.49	0.27
CV (%)	6.02	5.93	3.02	3.91	4.11	5.92

Note: Means followed by the same letter in a column are not significantly different at $P > 0.05$; W_1 , W_2 and W_3 (%v) indicate volumetric soil-water contents in percentage at the beginning, mid and end of growing stages of the plant, respectively; d_1 , d_2 and d_3 indicate soil sampling depths of 0-20 cm, 20-40 cm and 40-60 cm, respectively; M1 = 0N0P0FYM, M2 = 46N10P kg ha⁻¹, M3 = 5 t FYM ha⁻¹, M4 = 23N5P kg + 2.5 t FYM ha⁻¹, M5 = 46N10P kg + 2.5 t FYM ha⁻¹ and M6 = 23N5P kg + 5 t FYM ha⁻¹.

Table 5. Effect of Treatment Interaction on Volumetric Soil-Water Content at Different Plant Growth Stages and Soil Depths at Study Locations During the 2017 Cropping Season

Soil moisture conservation	Nutrient Management	Babile			Erer	
		W ₁ %v	W ₃ %v		W ₂ %v	W ₃ %v
		d1	d2	d3	d2	d1
Flatbed	0N0P0FYM ha ⁻¹	15.42h	2.99e	3.34d	5.39d	2.57cd
	46N10P kg ha ⁻¹	15.98gh	3.35c	3.43d	5.5d	2.73cd
	5 t FYM ha ⁻¹	17.62fg	3.61c	3.94c	6.05c	3.57b
	23N5P kg + 2.5 t FYM ha ⁻¹	17.49fg	3.46c	4.33c	5.69cd	3.3b
	46N10P kg + 2.5 t FYM ha ⁻¹	18.1ef	3.48c	3.76cd	5.58d	3.5b
	23N5P kg + 5 t FYM ha ⁻¹	18.53def	3.57c	4.06c	5.61cd	3.42b
Tied ridge	0N0P0FYM ha ⁻¹	22.49d	4.29d	4.46c	6.25cd	4.28a
	46N10P kg ha ⁻¹	22.0de	4.69c	4.96c	6.39c	3.74bc
	5 t FYM ha ⁻¹	28.043a	5.717b	5.8b	7.23ab	4.52a
	23N5P kg + 2.5 t FYM ha ⁻¹	27.68ab	5.48b	5.78b	6.8bc	4.18a
	46N10P kg + 2.5 t FYM ha ⁻¹	25.96bc	5.51b	5.87b	6.87b	3.99ab
	23N5P kg + 5 t FYM ha ⁻¹	25.75c	6.19a	6.55a	7.51a	4.3a
LSD (0.05)		1.88	0.35	0.59	1.023	1.104
CV (%)		5.21	4.65	7.14	4.2	6.13

Note: Means followed by the same letter in a column are not significantly different at $P > 0.05$; W_1 , W_2 and W_3 (%v) indicate volumetric soil-water contents in percentage at the beginning, heading and maturity stages of the plant, respectively; d_1 , d_2 and d_3 indicate soil sampling depths of 0-20 cm, 20-40 cm and 40-60 cm, respectively.

Water use efficiency (WUE)

Separate analysis results for water use efficiency data showed that biomass- and grain-WUE were significantly ($P < 0.05$) affected by both the main and interaction effects of soil moisture conservation and nutrient management for both study locations (Table 6).

Table 6. Mean Squares of ANOVA for Biomass and Grain WUE as a Function of Soil Moisture Conservation and Nutrient Management at Babile and Erer During the 2017 Cropping Season

Source	DF	Mean squares			
		Babile		Erer	
		WUE _{Biomass}	WUE _{Grain}	WUE _{Biomass}	WUE _{Grain}
REP	2	11.38	0.112	9.264	1.119
SMC	1	486.27**	76.432**	197.36*	33.81**
Error REP*SMC	2	0.546	0.0935	2.649	0.291
NM	5	67.04***	13.08***	59.9***	10.45***
SMC*NM	5	4.12***	0.592**	11.24***	0.674*

Error REP*SMC*NM	20	0.400	0.1103	1.066	0.2261
CV (%)		2.42	3.42	5.48	6.18

Note: *, ** and ***, Significant at $P < 0.05$, $P < 0.01$ and $P < 0.001$; NS = non-significant at $P > 0.05$; SMC = soil moisture conservation; NM = nutrient management; WUE_{Grain} = water use efficiency of grain and $WUE_{Biomass}$ = water use efficiency of dry biomass yield.

The mean difference for interactions of soil moisture conservation and nutrient management indicated that tied ridges with integrated nutrient amendments resulted in higher biomass- and grain-WUE than those recorded for flatbeds with nutrient amendments at both locations (Table 7). At Babile, tied ridges with the treatments M5 and M6 yielded the maximum biomass-WUE followed by those in tied ridges with M4 and sole FYM, in that order. Moreover, similar were the trends of the effect of treatments at Erer as well. However, the mean differences in biomass-WUE among flatbeds with nutrient amendments were not significant. However, the biomass-WUE of tied ridge treatment without nutrient amendment and flatbeds with integrated NP and FYM amendments did not vary significantly. The lowest biomass-WUE had been found from flatbed without nutrient amendment at Erer (Table 7). Overall, biomass-WUE had increased by 110% and 98% due to tied ridges with 46N10P kg + 2.5 t FYM ha⁻¹ as compared to unfertilized flatbeds at Babile and Erer, respectively. Grain-WUE for tied ridges with integrated NP and FYM, regardless of race, were maximal at Babile although with differences among them being non-significant, whereas at Erer the highest grain-WUE was recorded from tied ridges with 46N10P kg + 2.5 t FYM ha⁻¹ followed by treatment M6 and M4, in that order. At both locations, grain-WUE observed with sole applications of NP and FYM were at par regardless of moisture conservation practices (Table 7). Overall, the increase in grain-WUE due to tied ridges and 46N10P kg + 2.5 t FYM ha⁻¹ applications as compared to unfertilized flatbeds were 114% and 124% for Babile and Erer, respectively.

Table 7. Interaction Effects of Soil Moisture Conservation with Nutrient Management on Biomass- and Grain-WUE of Sorghum During 2017 Cropping Season

Soil moisture conservation	Nutrient management	Babile		Erer	
		$WUE_{Biomass}$	WUE_{Grain}	$WUE_{Biomass}$	WUE_{Grain}
Flatbed	0N0P0FYM ha ⁻¹	12.34 ^f	4.79 ^f	17.21 ^h	5.83 ^h
	46N10P kg ha ⁻¹	16.26 ^{de}	6.58 ^{de}	21.22 ^g	7.88 ^g
	5 t FYM ha ⁻¹	16.52 ^{de}	6.63 ^{cde}	22.11 ^g	8.23 ^g
	23N5P kg + 2.5 t FYM ha ⁻¹	18.7 ^{cd}	7.71 ^b	25.42 ^e	9.3 ^e
	46N10P kg + 2.5 t FYM ha ⁻¹	17.82 ^{cd}	7.43 ^{bc}	24.09 ^f	9 ^{ef}
	23N5P kg + 5 t FYM ha ⁻¹	17.3 ^{cde}	7.23 ^{bcd}	24.53 ^{ef}	9.33 ^e
Tied ridge	0N0P0FYM ha ⁻¹	14.75 ^{ef}	5.89 ^e	23.52 ^f	8.46 ^{fg}
	46N10P kg ha ⁻¹	18.88 ^{cd}	8.22 ^b	28.31 ^d	10.34 ^d
	5 t FYM ha ⁻¹	19.21 ^c	8.16 ^b	28.73 ^d	10.89 ^d
	23N5P kg + 2.5 t FYM ha ⁻¹	22.82 ^b	9.6 ^a	30.97 ^c	11.81 ^c
	46N10P kg + 2.5 t FYM ha ⁻¹	25.99 ^a	10.27 ^a	34.21 ^a	13.1 ^a
	23N5P kg + 5 t FYM ha ⁻¹	25.39 ^a	9.85 ^a	32.96 ^b	12.5 ^b
LSD (0.05)		1.759	0.81	1.078	0.566
CV (%)		5.48	6.18	2.42	3.42

Note: Means followed by the same letter in a column are not significantly different at $P > 0.05$, LSD, least significant difference and CV, coefficient of variation.

DISCUSSION

The amount of rainwater stored in the soil profile during the cropping season is important for plant growth in rainfed agriculture given the unreliable temporal distribution of rainfall in the study areas. The results described above clearly suggest that effective tillage techniques like tied ridging capture rainwater and store sufficient moisture in the soil that lasts for rainy periods and beyond for continued plant uptake to mitigate water stress during dry periods. These benefits of tied ridges facilitated by long ponding time allowing water to infiltrate [13] resulted in higher volumetric soil-water content, increased efficiency of moisture conservation and led to higher water use efficiency in

comparison to conventional flatbed planting method (farmers' practice). Mesfin *et al.* [14] have also made similar reports and McHugh *et al.* [15] found the volumetric soil moisture content to have increased by 24% at 0-15 cm depth and 9% at 30-45 cm depth in tied ridges as compared to conventional tillage. They also found with tied and open ridges 15-24% increase in seasonal soil-moisture content over the conventional flatbed planting method. The addition of organic materials to soil, as in our case, also increased soil water-holding capacity, which improved water availability to plants [16]. Moreover, the interaction between water conservation practice and nutrient management significantly improved both soil moisture retention and efficiency of moisture conservation. Thus, tied ridging amended with full FYM rate regardless of NP application caused the highest soil-water content as compared to other treatments during all three-measurement periods i.e., beginning, mid and end of growing seasons. The highest soil water storage in tied ridges with organic amendment might be attributed to the reduced run-off and increased infiltration due to the micro-catchment formed by the tied ridges and the soil water holding capacity improvement presumed to be acquired by farmyard manure application that led to higher soil-water content and higher efficiency of moisture conservation. Our findings, clearly suggest that the combined use of these practices in the rainfed farming of drylands might play a great role in mitigating dry spells and risk of crop failure and thus may help sustain crop production in such areas.

Naturally, the water use efficiency (WUE) which is a measure of a crop's capacity to convert water into plant biomass and grain also increased due to tied ridges amended with integrated NP and FYM in comparison to flatbed planting. Nutrient availability affects aboveground biomass, and canopy cover to reduce soil evaporation, plant residue production, nutrient dynamics in soil, and thereby improving crop growth and WUE [17]. Adequate nutrient supply particularly N and P have been shown to improve WUE in several crops [18,19]. The role of fertilizers in alleviation of drought stress is likely limited to cases where crops are nutrient-limited. In these situations, the addition of fertilizer results in plants that are more vigorous in growth and thus more capable of using available water. Nitrogen and phosphorous addition typically increase plant size, root growth and total leaf area. Greater root mass, root distribution, soil exploration and growth improve the plants' ability to access water from deep in the soil profile and thus the total amount of plant-available water as has been observed in our studies. Similarly, as total leaf area increases, in most instances the amount of potential water transpired by the plant increases leading to increased transpiration and higher yields achieved on account of higher WUE with particular reference to rainfed farming in semiarid areas of eastern Ethiopia.

CONCLUSION

In areas, like Babile and Erer districts of east Hararghe, where soil water and fertility are limiting for crop production, the use of improved technologies such as *in-situ* moisture conservation and integrated nutrient management are indispensable in agricultural operations. The results of these studies revealed that the integration of water conservation and nutrient management also enhanced sorghum grain- and biomass-WUE. The highest grain- and biomass-WUE were recorded in tied ridge treatment integrated with the application of half NP and full FYM rates. The sole applications of NP and FYM in their full rates resulted in lower performance concerning the above parameters as compared to when they were applied in combination, while the least performer was unfertilized flatbed planting. From the present findings, it also becomes clear that an integrated approach whereby water and nutrient imbalances have been addressed simultaneously provides optimum conditions for synergy between water conservation and nutrient management practices. It is also apparent that high rainfall if poorly distributed, may not necessarily translate to increased rainfall use efficiency. Therefore, emphasizing the need for such technologies enables farmers to fully capitalize on the entire rainfall season ensuring maximum capturing of any rainfall received particularly in semi-arid or drought-prone regions.

Further, the present studies also reflected on *in-situ* water conservation tillage that could be beneficial for improving soil moisture, efficiency of moisture conservation practices and WUE of grain sorghum. The results highlighted that the tied ridging with nutrient amendment can increase sorghum grain- and biomass-WUE up to 109 and 123 %, respectively, in the semi-arid agroecology of eastern Ethiopia where sorghum is increasingly grown. The use of fertilizers and/or manures with soil

moisture conservation has been found to have improved the water use efficiency of crops in semiarid areas. Thus, *in-situ* rainwater conservation practices should be part of the farming systems in semiarid lands. Therefore, tied ridging with integrated application of 46 kg N + 10 kg P + 2.5 tons FYM per hectare could be incorporated into the production practices of smallholder farmers in semi-arid Ethiopia, to increase the resilience of crop production systems against droughts, that predicted increase in frequency and severity because of climate change.

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CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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